

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

A REVIEW ON *TECOMA STANS***Shravan Kumar Dholi^{1*}, S. Ananditha Reddy², B. Srinidhi Reddy², E. Pramukhya²**¹ Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Vaageswari Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Beside LMD Police Station, Ramakrishna Colony, Karimnagar, T.S.-505481, India.² Department of Pharmacy, Vaageswari Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Beside LMD Police Station, Ramakrishna Colony, Karimnagar, T.S.-505481, India.**Abstract:**

Tecoma Stans, the yellow bells Plants belonging to the family Bignoniaceae. It height ranges from 2 to 4 meters. It is an important medicinal herb throughout India. Among all parts from Plant-seeds, roots and bark are the most important parts which are used medicinally. Now the present article gives updated on its pharmacological properties. These plants has more compound constituents are phytosterols, Alkaloids, quinines, amino acid, monoterpenes, activities for this plant are anti-diabetic, diuretic, anti-spasmodic, anti-microbial, anti-fungal and anti-oxidants.

Key words: *Tecoma Stans*, medicinal uses, herb.**Corresponding author:****Shravan Kumar Dholi,**

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Please cite this article in press as Shravan Kumar Dholi et al., A Review on *Tecoma Stans*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Plants are Cultured everywhere not in specific place. It useful to human health and well being. The plant is fast growing plant with 30 feet in height contents yellow flowers and leaves with green. The t.stan is useful to treat diabetes in mostly countries like Mexico, India and America and the roots are used to treat diuretic and Anti-fungal. The first prefer for this plant is herbal medicines. [1-5]

Vernacular (or) other names in other languages:

Hindi-Pillakaner

English-Yellow bells

Telugu-Paccha Pulu

Classification:

Common Name-Yellow trumpet bells

Kingdom-Plantae-Plants

Subkingdom-Tracheobionta-Vascular plants

Superdivision-Spermatophyta-Seed Plants

Division-Mangoliophyta-Flowering Plants

Class-Magnoliopsida-Dicotyledons

Subclass-Asteridae

Order-Scrophulariales

Family-Bignoniaceae-Trumpet-creeper family

Genus-Tecoma Juss,-trumpetbush P

Species-Tecoma Stans (L.) Juss. ex kunth-Yellow trumpetbush

Fig.1: TECOMA STANS plant

Chemical Constituents and Different Extracts of Tecoma Stans

Table 1: Analysis of different extracts of Tecoma Stan for different chemical constituents.

EXTRACTS

Components	Tests	Aqueous	Ethanol	n-Hexane
Alkaloids	Wagner	+	+	+
Coumarines	NaOH	+	+	+
Flavonoides	Salkowski	+	+	+
Sesquiterpen lactons	Baljet	+	+	+
Insaturacioens	KMno4	+	+	-
Esteroles and metilestteroles	Liebermann-Burchard	-	+	+
carbohydrates	Molish	+	-	-
Saponines	Liebermann-Burchard	-	+	+
Quinones	Bomtrager	-	+	-

Medicinal Use: Pharmacological Activities: T.stan has various pharmacological Activities anti-oxidant, anti diabetic, anti-fungal, anti-cancer, anti-hyperlipidemic, anti-microbial activities.

1. Anti-oxidant: The presents of Tannins in the extracts of bio-activities to posses' potent anti-oxidant activity.

2. Anti-spasmodic effect: This effect can be evaluated by using segment of ileum from rat with trade solution. The TLE dose dependently which indicate calcium channels are involved in this spasmolytic effect.

3. Anti-microbial activity: The extract of leaf was tested on Bacteria. The extract of phenolic content was showed its anti-microbial activity.

4. Anti fungal acitivity: The extract of t.stan was tested against two species of fungi (sporothrix schenckii and fonsecaea pedrosoi) Shows best effective anti-yeast and anti-fungal activity.

5. Anti-diabetic activity: TAE sub-chronic admin reduces triglycerides and cholesterol without modifying fasting glucose. The chemical composition of extract was analyzing their content of phenols, flavonoids and alkaloids reputed as to be responsible for hypo-glycemic properties of many anti diabetic

6. Wound healing property: The methanol extract of t.stans leaf was possess significant wound healing property.[6-10].

CONCLUSION:

Tecoma Stan is used by medical practitioners for treatment of various diseases. Pharmacological reviews on plants will give valuable information which will helpfull in getin more points about a plant species. As per my search the major activity has been use the leaves and flowers are use for treatment of

various diseases. We can wait and will find something new to cure any other new disease by this tecoma Stan.

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